

Kuchkarova Guljahon

English teacher at Secondary school N4, Uchkuprik district, Fergana region.

WORDS AND PHRASES EXPRESSING NEGATIVE EMOTIONS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGE

Abstract: This article deals with the expressing negative meaning words and phrases in the field of linguistics Phraseological units, which describe different human emotions such as delight, anger, worry, fear and others. In addition, these emotions, which are classified into positive and negative types. Furthermore, its main peculiarities, its importance of in the social life and the functional features of stylistics are highlighted in the article. As a result of our investigation, the following results were obtained:

- a) the increase in the need for the creation and significance of emotional lexicon, particularly words and phrases has been scientifically proved;
- b) the possibility of emotional words and phrases to represent the feelings of the people, culture and world outlook has been verified;
- c) the specificity of negative phrases has been revealed;
- d) the development of emotional style as a functional style has been grounded.

Keywords: Phraseologism (phraseological unit), anthropocentric paradigm, positive emotions, negative emotions, human, psycho-emotional state.

INTRODUCTION

Emotional lexicon is a specific layer of vocabulary in each language, formed under

the influence of linguistic phenomenon, with a wide scope. It is natural that this linguistic phenomenon, namely the emotional lexicon, is an essential component of any society's existence, as well as an important factor in human development. In addition, it well known that word and phrases that express the emotional experiences and commands of the linguistics. The fact that words and expressions in speech activities express the speakers' intend and desire is the main topic of linguistic research.

Research methods. Interest in emotional lexicon has grown significantly in recent

years and many modern members of society, regardless of nationality and profession, have began to finding answers to today's unanswered questions in the linguistic books. Words and phrases expressing negative emotions significantly determine the worldview and perception of the world, the value system and the image of the universe of all peoples.

Negative lexicon contain information about human emotions, and therefore, they are

valuable source of knowledge about people's life, traditions and culture. Emotional lexicon have always been the object of scientific research in various fields of human knowledge, including philosophers, historians, linguists, psychologists, cultural scientists and others.

Many scientists emphasize that the concept of the emotional words is a special type

of text (R.Qo'ng'urov, Vinogradov, Volf E.M, Ivin A.A, Tugarinov V.P, Abdullayev A, Safarov), moreover, a special type of text is currently distinguished in linguistics.

Results and discussion: Negative emotional words and phrases are also noted as a

special type of text that reflects traditions, as well as the living spiritual culture of the people. Among human emotions fear plays a special role and a sufficient number of expressions denoting fear were found in both analyzed languages. So, The English

phraseology frighten (or scare) somebody out of his senses means “to scare someone till losing consciousness” *1+.

There are various levels of fear. For instance, in the following expressions, fear

acquires the highest point of intensity: (as) scared as a rabbit – scared out of consciousness[2].

We all know that people experiences various emotional states throughout their lives.

Under the influence of such emotional states, he reacts to the external and internal worlds in various ways, expressing his emotions and feelings in numerous ways. People frequently express their emotions through words or gestures. As in all languages, Uzbek language have methods and tools that create emotional expressiveness. A. Abdullayev an uzbek linguist claimed that the phonetic phonological, lexical-phonological, morphological and syntactic methods of expressing emotional-expressiveness [3]

He mentioned the following methods for improving phonetic meaning in modern

Uzbek. language: 1) strong pronunciation of the vowel (stress); 2) vowel lengthening

(quantitative stress); 3) consonant doubling (gemination); There are specific conditions and rules for the usage of the listed phonetic phenomena. Furthermore, the linguist claims that some forms of expressive expression in the phonetic method, in addition to strengthening and weakening, express meanings such as caressing and kissing [4].

Many of the girls «ooooohed!» at the sight of the unicorn. «Oooh it's so beautiful!»

whispered Lavender Brown (J.K. Rowlin. Harry Potter and the Goblet of Fire)

O'ZBEK TILIDA

– Raxmat, Xofiz aka, bi-ir miriqdik suhbatingizdan. Shunaqa kelib turing... Otamlashish yaxshi narsa-,da, a? (T.Malik.Shaytanat,2-kitob)

Yuribman qarichlab o'lcha-ab,- dedi Kesakpolvon yana zarda bilan. Keyin ichida

“Qidirasan-a, qidirasan, yo'q bo'lib ketsam, do'ppingni osmonga otarsan!” (

T.Malik.Shaytanat,3-kitob)

In linguistics, phraseological units are stable word combinations, and the meaning of a phraseological unit is not consists of the meanings of the words that comprise it. Phraseological units include the following types of phrases: idioms, collocations, proverbs, sayings, grammatical phraseological units and phraseological schemes. The field of English phraseology is large and varied. Every aspect of research is deserving of the attention it receive.

Phraseologisms, that are functionally correlated with a noun are considered substantive. That is, the core component of substantive phraseological units is a noun. For instance: a drop in the bucket -a very small amount; All the money we raised was just a drop in the bucket. Small amounts of money.

Wind bag -an exhaustively talkative person; to hit the roof –to become very angry;

once in a blue moon- very rarely; full of beans –vivid and full of energy;

b) Verb phraseological units

Verbal phraseologisms are those that can be functionally correlated with a verb. That is, the verb is the primary component of such phraseological units.

For instance: drive smb up a wall- is very annoying; sell smb down the river-betray;

put smth on ice – delay, postpone; shoot the breeze- chatting informally about

unimportant things;

c) Adjective phraseological units

Adjectives should be considered phraseological units that are functionally correlated

with adjectives, meaning that the adjective is their core component. The proportion of the studied adjective phraseological units in the total volume is statistically insignificant.

For instance: On cloud nine- when someone is on cloud nine, it means that he or she is feeling extremely happy.

Example: When he finally proposed to her, she was on cloud nine.

Spaced out-when you are not concentrating on what is going on around you, you can say you are spaced out or daydreaming.

Example: Dave, are you listening? You look totally spaced out!

Shaken up - after people receive shocking news or experience something unexpected, they may feel shaken up. It means to be shocked or very surprised.

Example: After the accident she was completely shaken up.

On pins and needles -when people say they're on pins and needles, they aren't talking about sewing or injections. It really means that they are feeling anxious or nervous.

Example: The movie was so suspenseful, I was on pins and needles the whole time!

In learning English as a second language, it's important to know how to express your feelings. It will enable you to put your English vocabulary knowledge to work and interact more fluently with native English speakers. We can always use such expressions as I feel a little low/depressed, anger. In this situations expressing your feelings with idioms, phrases or slang it sounds like a natural.

IN THE FOLLOWING EXAMPLES ARE USED IN SAD SITUATIONS

1. Down in the mouth- expresses sadness means to look unhappy or sad. This idiom is never used to describe oneself. It is always used to describe another person.

She seems to be down in the mouth. Maybe she failed her exams.

Nina seems to be down in the dumps because she broke up with her boyfriend recently.

2. Reduce to tears - to make someone cry or to be so unhappy and down that, you begin to cry.

My boss reduced me to tears with his constant criticism today.

3. Lump in your throat - when we watch an emotional movie (for example a drama like Titanic), we get a feeling in our throat that means we are about to cry. We are upset, sad, and we worry about the main characters of the film.

His speech was so emotional that I lumped my throat.

4. Feeling blue/to have the blues - the color blue is associated with depression, a bad mood and sadness. It is used when talking about ourselves or others, but the phrase have the blues is usually used to speak about others.

She has the blues today. / I was feeling blue yesterday.

5. Face like a wet weekend- it can be used when a person wants to relax, do

something outdoors or get some fresh air on the weekend but is unable to do so because the weather is poor - it's overcast, cold or constantly raining, which makes the person sad or depressed.

Billy, your face is like a wet weekend. What's wrong?

Such idioms and phrases can be found not only in English but also in Uzbek. When

comparing phraseological units in English and Uzbek language, phraseological units are similar in structure can be found. When analyzing them, it should be noted the in structure, imagery and stylistic coloring. The fund of uzbek phraseology is replete with national and borrowed, terminological and non- terminological, just like the fund of English Phraseology.

In Uzbek phraseology conveys various levels of human fear: zir titramoq- to be very afraid (of someone); to tremble (before someone)like an aspen leaf [5].

Busy as a bee – aridek band

To play with fire- olov bilan o'ynashmoq

To put the cart before the horse- ishni pachavasini chiqarmoq

To oil the wheels – pora bermoq

A wolf in sheeps clothing – eng xavfli dushman

A bad egg- yomon odam

To sell the pass – hoyinlik qilmoq

There are such idioms in uzbek: Tapa sochi tikka bo'lmoq; Tarvuzi qo'ltigidan

tushmoq; Kovushini to'g'rilab qo'ymoq; To'nini teskari kiymoq; Qo'lini paxsa qilmoq; Moshxo'rdaga qatiq bo'lmoq

Conclusion. Thus, a large number of units describing a wide range of human emotions have been identified in the phraseology of the English and Uzbek languages. They are actively used in a literary text as a source of studying the character's and author's vocabulary, as well as a link between them. The lexical set of characters' speech occasionally contradicts the work's style and genre, creating a "conflict" between different types of verbal expression of thought. It should be noted here that a work of art frequently contains more than one character, indicating the operation of entirely different verbal complexes, which, in turn, form different pictures of the world and perception.

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